

Sustainable materials in rigid pavement construction contribute to environmental protection and resource efficiency

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KEYWORDS

Fly Ash, GGBS, Natural Fibers, Bamboo Fiber, Coconut Fiber, Human Hair Fiber..

ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for sustainable and durable construction materials in the field of transportation infrastructure has led to the exploration of alternative materials in rigid pavement construction. This research investigates the strength and durability characteristics of rigid pavement concrete incorporating Fly Ash, Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS), and Natural Fibers as partial replacements and additives to conventional concrete. In this study, Fly Ash and GGBS were used as supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) to partially replace ordinary Portland cement, while natural fibers such as bamboo, coconut & human hair were added to enhance the tensile strength and crack resistance of the concrete. Various mix proportions were designed and tested to evaluate the mechanical properties including compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength. Durability aspects such as water absorption, acid resistance, and sulfate resistance were also assessed under different curing conditions. The experimental results revealed that the partial replacement of cement with Fly Ash and GGBS significantly improved the workability and long-term strength of the concrete. The inclusion of natural fibers contributed to better post-cracking behavior and resistance against surface deterioration. An optimal mix was identified that offers a balanced improvement in both strength and durability properties, making it a viable solution for rigid pavement applications. This study highlights the potential of using industrial by-products and eco-friendly fibers in concrete to develop cost-effective, durable, and environmentally sustainable rigid pavements, aligning with modern infrastructure goals.

1. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry plays a crucial role in global infrastructure development but is also one of the largest contributors to environmental pollution and resource depletion. Rigid pavements, commonly used in highways, airports, and industrial flooring, require large quantities of cement and aggregates, leading to high carbon emissions and excessive consumption of natural resources. The production of Portland cement, a key component of concrete, is responsible for nearly 8% of global CO₂ emissions, making it imperative to explore alternative materials that can reduce the environmental footprint of pavement construction. The increasing demand for sustainable construction practices has driven research into the use of alternative materials, such as natural fibers and industrial by-products, which can enhance the durability and performance of rigid pavements while reducing reliance on non-renewable resources. Among the promising materials, bamboo fiber, coconut fiber, and human hair fiber stand out due to their natural availability, high tensile strength, and biodegradable nature. These fibers improve the mechanical properties of concrete, enhancing its tensile strength, crack resistance, and overall durability. Additionally, industrial by-products such as ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS) and fly ash provide an eco-friendly substitute for cement, lowering greenhouse gas emissions and promoting waste utilization in construction. Bamboo fiber has gained attention for its high strength-to-weight ratio, flexibility, and biodegradability. It has been successfully incorporated into concrete to improve tensile strength and reduce crack formation. Coconut fiber, another natural fiber, possesses excellent toughness and resistance to water absorption, making it a valuable reinforcement material in rigid pavement construction. Human hair fiber, often regarded as waste, has been found to enhance bonding in concrete while offering additional tensile reinforcement, which can help in reducing the brittleness of conventional concrete. Industrial by-products like GGBFS and fly ash have been widely studied for their pozzolanic properties, which contribute to improved durability and long-term performance of concrete structures. GGBFS, a by-product of the steel manufacturing industry, is known to increase concrete strength, enhance sulfate

resistance, and improve overall durability when used as a partial cement replacement. Similarly, fly ash, a residue from coal combustion, enhances workability, reduces water demand, and improves the long-term strength of concrete. These materials contribute to sustainability by minimizing waste disposal issues and reducing the carbon footprint of cement production. This study aims to bridge the gap in research by evaluating the feasibility, mechanical properties, and environmental impact of incorporating these sustainable materials in rigid pavement construction. Through laboratory testing and comparative analysis, the research will provide insights into the performance and durability of modified pavement mixes, contributing to the development of sustainable construction practices. By promoting the use of renewable and waste-derived materials, this study aligns with global efforts to achieve environmental protection, resource efficiency, and sustainable development in the construction industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Sustainable concrete for rigid pavement construction using de-hydroxylated Kaolinitic clay: Mechanical and microstructural properties (2019)-

The increasing demand for sustainable construction materials has prompted research into alternative substances that can enhance the mechanical and microstructural properties of concrete. The study conducted by Busari et al. (2019) explores the viability of using de-hydroxylated Kaolinitic clay (DHKC) as a partial replacement for cement in self-compacting concrete for rigid pavement construction. This research contributes to the ongoing efforts to find eco-friendly materials that can reduce construction costs while maintaining structural integrity. Numerical Optimization and Performance Analysis Through response surface analysis, the researchers established relationships between the mechanical properties of the concrete and varying DHKC content. The optimal flexural strength was predicted to be 4.86 MPa, achieved with a specific combination of metakaolin content and concrete age. Notably, the maximum compressive strength was observed at 110 days of curing, highlighting the importance of time in the development of concrete strength. It concluded that de-hydroxylated

Kaolinitic clay is a viable and eco-friendly alternative in concrete technology, particularly for rigid pavement construction. The research advocates for the integration of sustainable supplementary materials to improve the mechanical properties of concrete while promoting environmental sustainability. These findings have significant implications for the construction industry, encouraging the exploration of innovative materials to meet the challenges of modern infrastructure development.

2.2. Sustainable pavement construction: A systematic literature review of environmental and economic analysis of recycled materials (2021)

The increasing generation of waste in various sectors, including municipal, commercial, and construction industries, has led to significant environmental challenges. The construction sector, specifically pavement construction, can play a crucial role in mitigating these issues by utilizing recycled materials. The systematic literature review by Salehi et al. (2021) focuses on the environmental and economic implications of using recycled materials in pavement construction, highlighting the necessity of integrating sustainable practices into infrastructure development.

2.3. Sustainable Pavement Material for Enhanced Road Performance and Environmental Impact Reduction (2023)

The construction and maintenance of road infrastructure present significant challenges related to both road performance and environmental sustainability. In this context, Shadab Akhtar and Ankit Sethi's (2023) study published in the International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science explores the development and evaluation of sustainable pavement materials, specifically focusing on recycled concrete aggregate (RCA). This review summarizes the key findings and implications of their research. The findings of Akhtar and Sethi's study underscore the potential of RCA as a sustainable pavement material that balances road performance with environmental considerations.

2.4. Use of Waste Materials for Sustainable Development of Rigid Pavement (2023)

In the context of sustainable construction, the responsible use of Earth's natural resources is crucial for future generations. The research article by Al-Hindawi et al. (2023) from the International Journal of Engineering

focuses on utilizing waste materials to enhance sustainability in rigid pavement construction. This study highlights the environmental and economic benefits of incorporating waste concrete and ground-granulated blast-furnace slag (GGBFS) as partial replacements in cement-based materials. The study provides essential insights for civil engineers and policymakers focusing on sustainable infrastructure development. By adopting practices that incorporate recycled materials, stakeholders can significantly reduce the environmental impacts of road construction while ensuring the performance and longevity of rigid pavements.

2.5. Sustainable Designed Pavement Materials (2020)

The editorial by Yue Xiao et al. (2020) in the journal Materials provides an overview of a special issue dedicated to recent advancements in the field of sustainable pavement materials. With increasing environmental concerns in construction, the emphasis on developing eco-friendly pavement materials has become crucial for sustainable infrastructure development. The editorial underscores the critical need for research and development in sustainable pavement materials, emphasizing the role of recycling and modification in reducing the environmental footprint of pavement construction. The highlighted themes reflect a holistic approach to sustainability in civil engineering, incorporating material science, environmental considerations, and innovative technologies.

2.6. Utilization Of Waste Materials in The Construction of Rigid Pavement: A Review (2024)

The review article by Suryakant Maurya and Mr. Ushendra Kumar (2024) published in the International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) discusses the pressing need for sustainable practices in the construction industry, particularly concerning rigid pavements. The study emphasizes the significant environmental and economic benefits of utilizing waste materials in construction, reflecting a growing trend toward sustainability in civil engineering. The review article provides a comprehensive examination of the current trends in utilizing waste materials for rigid pavement construction, emphasizing the dual benefits of resource conservation and improved pavement performance. It serves as a valuable resource for future research and practical applications aimed at advancing sustainable infrastructure development.

2.7. How sustainable are flexible and rigid pavement? A Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) approach (2020)

The study titled "How sustainable are flexible and rigid pavement? A Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) approach" by J U D Hatmoko and L Lendra (2021), published in the IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering, explores the environmental impacts associated with the construction of flexible and rigid pavements. The research employs the Eco-Indicator 99 (EI99) methodology to assess various life cycle stages, providing insights into the sustainability of these pavement types. The findings highlight the need for further investigations into the long-term sustainability of rigid pavements and the potential for optimizing their design and material usage. Additionally, the development of improved maintenance strategies for rigid pavements could further enhance their sustainability profile.

2.8. Sustainable Pavement Construction in Sensitive Environments: Low-Energy Asphalt with Local Waste Materials and Geomaterials (2024)

The study titled "Sustainable Pavement Construction in Sensitive Environments: Low-Energy Asphalt with Local Waste Materials and Geomaterials" by Miguel A. Franesqui, Jorge Yepes, and Samuel Valencia-Díaz, (2024), explores innovative approaches to enhance the sustainability of asphalt pavements. The research emphasizes the integration of low-energy asphalt technologies, waste recycling, and the utilization of local geomaterials, particularly in volcanic environments where unique challenges arise. The findings of this study underscore the potential for low-energy asphalt techniques combined with local waste materials to significantly enhance the sustainability of pavement construction in sensitive environments. By optimizing the use of recycled materials and reducing energy consumption, the research advocates for eco-efficient asphalt pavements that can effectively address both environmental concerns and engineering requirements.

2.9. Review of the Engineering Properties of Concrete with Paper Mill Waste Ash – Towards Sustainable Rigid Pavement Construction (2020)

The review paper titled "A Review of the Engineering Properties of Concrete with Paper Mill Waste Ash – Towards Sustainable Rigid Pavement Construction" by Deveshan L. Pillay, Oladimeji B. Olalusi, and Mohamed

M.H. Mostafa, (2020), explores the use of paper mill waste ash (PMA) as a partial replacement for cement in concrete. This investigation is prompted by the pressing need for sustainable construction practices, particularly in the context of rigid pavement construction. The review concludes that paper mill waste ash is a viable alternative binder material for sustainable rigid pavement construction. The superior mechanical properties coupled with its low environmental impact position PMA as a promising solution for reducing the ecological footprint of concrete production. This review serves as a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners in the construction industry, providing insights into the potential of PMA as a sustainable material in concrete applications.

2.10. Sustainable Pavement Construction: A Comprehensive Review on the Use of Recycled Materials and their Impact on Performance (2023)

The article titled "Sustainable Pavement Construction: A Comprehensive Review on the Use of Recycled Materials and their Impact on Performance" by Aditya Jakhar and Rahul Meena, (2023), discusses the growing emphasis on sustainable practices within the construction industry, particularly focusing on pavement construction. This review critically examines the effectiveness of various recycled materials as viable substitutes for conventional materials, contributing to both sustainability and performance optimization in pavement engineering. This comprehensive review underscores the potential of various recycled materials to enhance sustainability in pavement construction. By addressing environmental concerns and optimizing performance, the incorporation of recycled materials presents a pathway for the construction industry to meet modern demands for sustainability. The findings provide valuable insights for researchers, engineers, and policymakers aiming to advance sustainable infrastructure practices.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

3.1 MATERIALS USED

This study utilizes a combination of traditional and sustainable materials in the construction of rigid pavement. The primary materials used include:

- 1. Cement:** The base material providing strength and binding properties. IS 1489 1991 Part I defining PPC as "An intimately inter ground mixture of Portland clinker and pozzolana with the possible addition of gypsum

(natural or chemical) or an intimate and uniform blending of Portland cement and fine pozzolana". Portland-pozzolana cement can be produced either by grinding together Portland cement clinker and pozzolana with addition of gypsum or calcium sulphate, or by intimately and uniformly blending Portland cement and fine pozzolana. The pozzolanic materials generally used for manufacture of PPC are calcined clay or fly ash. Portland-pozzolana cement produces less heat of hydration and offers greater resistance to the attack of aggressive waters than normal Portland cement. Moreover, it reduces the leaching of calcium hydroxide liberated during the setting and hydration of cement.

2. Aggregates: Fine and coarse aggregates ensuring stability and strength.

1. Fine Aggregate: Aggregates are the important constituents in concrete. They give body to the concrete, reduce shrinkage and effect economy. They occupy about 70-80 percent of the volume of the concrete. Aggregates shall consist of naturally occurring (crushed or uncrushed) stones, gravel and sand or combination thereof. They shall be hard, strong, durable, clear and free from veins and adherent coating, and free from injurious amounts of disintegrated pieces, alkali, vegetable matter and other deleterious substances. As far as possible, flaky, and elongated pieces should be avoided. Aggregates can be mainly classified into fine aggregates and coarse aggregates. IS 383- 1970 defining fine aggregates as "Aggregate most of which passes 4.75mm IS sieve and contains only so much coarser material as permitted." It may be:

2. Coarse Aggregate: IS 383-1970 defines coarse aggregates as Aggregates most of which is retained on 4.75 mm IS Sieve and containing only so much finer material as is permitted for the various types described in this standard Figure 3.2.

Coarse aggregates may be described as:

- I. Uncrushed gravel or stone which results from natural disintegration of rock,
- II. Crushed gravel or stone when it results from crushing of gravel or hard stone, and
- III. Partially crushed gravel or stone when it is a product of the blending of uncrushed gravel stone and crushed gravel or stone.

3. Water: Used for hydration and chemical reactions in concrete. According to IS 456: 2000, water used for mixing and curing shall be clean and free from injurious

amounts of oils, acids, alkalis, salts, sugar, organic materials, or other substances that may be deleterious to concrete or steel. Potable water is generally considered satisfactory for mixing concrete. The pH value of water shall be not less than 6.

4. Bamboo Fiber: A natural fiber known for its high tensile strength and flexibility, incorporated to enhance crack resistance. Processed coconut Fiber is used in this research. They are properly washed and drawn into strands before use. Treatment of fibres removes dust and other residual particles left on the fibre to augment the surface of contact between the fibre and mix resulting in better binding between the reinforcement and concrete and ultimately higher strength. The fibre is washed in tap water for 30 minutes to loosen the fibres and to remove the coir dust. Fibres are then washed and soaked again for 30 minutes. This process is to be repeated three times The softened fibres are straightened manually and combed with a steel comb. To accelerate the drying process, the wet long fibres will be then put in oven at 30°C for 10–12 in which most of the moisture will be removed. The fibres are then completely dried in the open air, combed again and finally cut into the required length of 5cm and soaked in oil for 15-20 min and dried in sun for 24 hours.

5. Coconut Fiber: Provides enhanced durability and prevents shrinkage cracks. Bamboo fibres with size of varying length from 2 to 4 cm, breadth from 1 to 2 cm, and thickness of 1 cm is also used as a partial replacement of coarse aggregate at the replacement levels of 0%, 2%, 4% and 5%. The physical properties of all these materials were tested as per IS 383-1970.

6. Human Hair Fiber: Improves tensile strength and enhances bonding within the concrete matrix. Human hair made up from the human being. Human hair was about 65%-95% of its weight its proteins, more than 32% of water, lipid pigment and other component they made it by processing of chemical synthesis. The human hair fiber controls the crack because of drying and plastic shrinkage. The hair fiber is low at cost and its form in huge quantity. In the study the effect of RHA as a partial cement replacing material with addition of human hair fiber were carried out the experiment were conducted on concrete cube, beam, and cylinder of standard sizes.

7. Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS): A by-product of the steel industry used as a partial replacement for cement to improve durability and

sustainability. Concrete manufacturing involves the use of additional cementitious materials, leading to increased carbon dioxide emissions, which contribute to environmental degradation by affecting the Earth's protective layers. To mitigate this impact, cement was replaced with varying percentages of Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS) in this study. The replacement levels considered were 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%. Various tests, including compressive strength tests on cubes, cylinders, and beams, were conducted to assess the performance of GGBS-incorporated concrete.

8. Fly Ash: A by-product of coal combustion that enhances workability and reduces environmental impact. Fly ash closely resembles the volcanic ashes that were historically used in producing the earliest known hydraulic cements approximately 2,300 years ago. These ancient cements were manufactured near the small Italian town of Pozzuoli, which later lent its name to the term "pozzolan." A pozzolan is a siliceous or siliceous-aluminous material that, when combined with lime and water, forms a cementitious compound. Among the various pozzolanic materials, fly ash is the most widely known and extensively used worldwide. However, it is also a notorious waste product generated by coal-based electricity-producing thermal power plants, including the Koradi Thermal Power Plant in Nagpur. Fly ash is often associated with severe environmental issues such as soil degradation, surface and groundwater pollution, air pollution, and adverse health effects on humans. In response to these concerns, researchers have explored multiple avenues for reusing fly ash across various applications. One of the most effective and widely adopted methods is its incorporation into cement concrete. Fly ash particles, being nearly spherical in shape, facilitate smooth blending and flow within concrete mixtures.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental investigation aimed to evaluate the performance of bamboo fiber, coconut fiber, human hair fiber, fly ash, and ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS) in rigid pavement concrete. Various tests were conducted to determine the mechanical properties, durability, and workability of the modified concrete mixtures. The test results provided valuable insights into

the enhancement of concrete properties using these sustainable materials.

4.1.1 Human Hair Fiber

Human hairs have been used as fibre here and they have been washed as well after collection to remove any dust particles or any undesirable impurity present and after washing hairs are properly dried either under sun or in oven and preferably should be sorted such as they have uniform length to maintain and have an even and equal distribution of hairs while mixing concrete. After drying hair can be stored without any issue of odour or decay. The diameter of hair used is 100 to 120µm. The length of hair is 60mm. Aspect ratio used is 500-600. Tensile strength of Human hair fibre is 380MPa. The ultimate tensile strain used is 50.16%. As per Indian standard concrete cube of size 150X150X150mm was casted and curing was done for 7days 14days and 28days, Test were performed by using compressive strength testing machine. The percentage of human hair were taken as 0%, 1%, 2%,3% and 4%. Three cubes of each percentage of human hair are casted. After the test results were taken are shown in below tabular form.

Table 4.1 Compressive Strength of Concrete

SN	Curing Age	% Hair	M20 Strength (MPa)	M30 Strength (MPa)
1	7 days	0%	14.90	22.35
2	14 days	0%	18.40	27.60
3	28 days	0%	22.30	33.45
4	7 days	1%	17.65	26.48
5	14 days	1%	19.65	29.48
6	28 days	1%	23.50	35.25
7	7 days	2%	18.87	28.31
8	14 days	2%	21.35	32.03
9	28 days	2%	24.56	36.84
10	7 days	3%	20.63	30.95
11	14 days	3%	22.14	33.21
12	28 days	3%	24.93	37.40
13	7 days	4%	19.50	29.25
14	14 days	4%	20.35	30.53
15	28 days	4%	23.60	35.40

Fig.4.1: Compressive strength of M30 grade concrete at various % of human hair

Observations from the Graph:

- Strength Increases with Hair % Up to 3%:
 - At all curing ages (7, 14, and 28 days), the compressive strength increases as the hair content increases from 0% to 3%.
- Peak Strength at 3% Hair Content:
 - The maximum strength is observed at 3% hair addition:
 - 7 days: 30.95 MPa
 - 14 days: 33.21 MPa
 - 28 days: 37.40 MPa
- Slight Decrease at 4% Hair:
 - A minor reduction in strength is observed when hair content is increased to 4%, indicating possible fiber clustering or poor bonding at higher content.
- Consistent Strength Gain with Age:
 - For each percentage of hair, compressive strength increases progressively from 7 to 28 days.

4.1.2 Bamboo

Bamboo fibres with size of varying length from 2 to 4 cm, breadth from 1 to 2 cm, and thickness of 1 cm is also used as a partial replacement of coarse aggregate at the replacement levels of 0%, 2%, 4% and 5%. The physical properties of all these materials were tested as per IS 383-1970.

Table 4.2: Compressive Strength (N/mm²) for Bamboo Fiber Concrete

Bamboo %	7 Days (MPa)	28 Days (MPa)	56 Days (MPa)
0%	25.049	48.608	54.833
2%	22.434	43.334	50.115
4%	18.717	39.233	45.668
5%	15.968	35.534	42.434

Fig.4.2: Compressive strength of M30 grade concrete at various % of Bamboo

Observations from the Graph (M30 Grade Concrete):

- Decrease in Strength with Bamboo Addition:
 - As the percentage of bamboo increases, compressive strength decreases consistently across all curing durations (7, 28, and 56 days).
- Highest Strength at 0% Bamboo:
 - The highest compressive strength is observed with 0% bamboo, indicating that the inclusion of bamboo fibers weakens the concrete matrix in this case.
- Rate of Decrease:
 - The drop in strength is more noticeable from 0% to 2% and 2% to 4%, suggesting a sharp initial impact of bamboo addition.
 - From 4% to 5%, the decrease is still evident but relatively slower, hinting at a threshold behavior.
- Curing Time Impact:
 - Strength increases over time (from 7 to 56 days) for all percentages, showing good curing behavior.
 - However, the percentage gain with curing decreases as bamboo content increases.

4.1.3 Coconut Fiber

This study aimed at analyzing the variation in strength of coconut fiber (oil coated raw and oil coated processed fibres) reinforced concrete at varying fibre contents and to compare it with that of conventional concrete. The various strength aspects analyzed are the compressive strength of the coconut fiber reinforced concrete at varying percentages (4%,5%,6% by the weight of cement) of fibre. The influence of shape of fibre on strength is also studied by testing on coconut fibre mesh of predetermined dimensions. The optimal percentage of both the processed fibre strands and raw fibre meshes were found out by trial and error and the optimum percentage of superplasticizer needed for the required workability was also determined. The calculated amount of cement and fine aggregate are mixed till a uniform mix is obtained. The amounts of fibre adopted are 4%, 5% and 6% of cement. Coir fibre strands are cut into a length of 5cm washed, oil coated with coconut oil and dried in sunlight for 24 hours. It is then added to the mix until a uniform colour is obtained. Coarse aggregates are then added to the same and mixed followed by addition of water. Care should be taken to add water slowly in stages to prevent bleeding which may affect the strength formation of concrete rising of water required for hydration to the surface. Admixture is added towards the last stage of addition of water to avail sufficient time for mixing before the concrete hardens. It is placed in the mould, compacted, and finished cubes each of the same are prepared and cured. The compressive strength for 7day and 28 day is determined.

Compressive Strength of CFRC (Processed): Coconut fibre reinforced concrete was added to concrete at varying proportions (4%, 5%, 6% of that of weight of cement) at a water cement ratio of 0.5 The desired slump value and compressive strength was obtained for conventional concrete at this ratio. However, when fibre is added to the mix low workability was observed. Hence superplasticizer was added at different proportions of cement to get a concrete mix of suitable workability.

Table 4.3: Compressive Strength of M30 CFRC (PROCESSED)

Specimen	W/C Ratio	% Coconut Fibre	% Superplasticizer	Slump (mm)	7-Day Strength (N/mm ²)	28-Day Strength (N/mm ²)
1	0.38	4%	0.3%	110	22.5	38.00
2	0.36	5%	0.4%	105	24.8	40.50
3	0.35	6%	0.8%	105	23.6	39.00

Fig.4.3: Compressive strength of M30 grade concrete at various % of Coconut

Observations from Graphs:

Effect of Coconut Fibre Content:

- Strength increases from 38.00 MPa at 4% fibre to a peak of 40.50 MPa at 5%.
- A slight decline to 39.00 MPa at 6% indicates that too much fibre may start to reduce strength due to poor workability or fibre agglomeration.

Effect of Water-Cement (W/C) Ratio:

- Lower W/C ratios generally result in higher strength (specimen 2: 0.36 → 40.5 MPa).
- However, extremely low W/C ratios (like 0.35) may not significantly improve strength and can cause workability issues.

Effect of Superplasticizer:

- Higher superplasticizer (0.8%) doesn't necessarily lead to higher strength (specimen 3 shows a drop).
- Optimal dosages seem to balance workability and strength.

Slump Observations:

- Highest slump at 110 mm (specimen 1) corresponds to lowest strength.
- As slump reduces slightly, compressive strength improves, suggesting better mix cohesiveness at slightly lower workability.

4.1.4 Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS)

Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS) has the potential to enhance the stability characteristics of concrete when compared to a control mix. This project focuses on evaluating the impact of replacing cement with varying percentages of GGBS, specifically at 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50%. By incorporating GGBS as a partial substitute for cement, the study aims to assess its influence on the strength, durability, and overall performance of concrete. The use of GGBS not only contributes to sustainability by utilizing an industrial byproduct but also enhances various properties of concrete, such as reduced heat of hydration, improved workability, and long-term strength development. The investigation will include a comparative analysis of the control mix and GGBS-modified concrete to determine the optimal replacement level that ensures structural stability while promoting eco-friendly construction practices.

Table 4.4: Compressive Strength M30 on Cubes using Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS)

Mix Type	7 Days (M30)	14 Days (M30)	28 Days (M30)
Normal Concrete	20.80	25.60	30.00
GGBS 5%	21.46	25.60	30.96
10%	21.73	26.40	32.08
20%	22.13	29.28	32.54
30%	22.80	30.00	34.22
40%	17.07	20.65	23.12
50%	14.66	17.05	20.47

Fig.4.4: Compressive strength of M30 grade concrete at various % of Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS)

Observations from Graphs:

- Strength Gain with GGBS (up to 30%):
 - Compressive strength increases steadily from 5% to 30% GGBS.
 - Maximum 28-day strength is at 30% GGBS (34.22 MPa), which is ~14% higher than normal concrete.
- Performance Drop Beyond 30% GGBS:
 - At 40% and 50%, all strength values drop noticeably.
 - 50% GGBS shows significantly lower strength (20.47 MPa at 28 days), making it unsuitable for structural M30 concrete.
- Early Strength (7 & 14 Days):
 - Up to 30% GGBS, early strength improves modestly.
 - Beyond 30%, early-age strength reduction is clear—this suggests slower hydration or poor early-age gain due to excess GGBS.

4.1.5 Fly Ash

Fly ash, a waste generated by thermal power plants, poses a significant environmental concern due to its disposal challenges and potential ecological impact. This study focuses on the utilization of fly ash in cement concrete as a partial replacement of cement, as well as an additive, to develop a sustainable and environmentally friendly method for its disposal and reuse. The research specifically examines the application of fly ash in concrete mixtures, replacing cement in varying proportions ranging from 5% to 25% in incremental steps of 5%. This investigation serves as a case study for the Koradi Thermal Power Plant in Nagpur, Maharashtra, evaluating the feasibility and benefits of incorporating fly ash in concrete production. The findings aim to highlight the potential of fly ash as a supplementary cementitious material, reducing dependency on conventional cement while promoting sustainable construction practices. In the present study, M30 grade concrete with a nominal mix design, as per IS 456-2000, was used. The concrete mix proportion, in terms of volume ratio with a water-cement ratio of 0.5. Fly ash was blended into the cement at varying replacement levels ranging from 5% to 25% by weight of cement, increasing in steps of 5%. For compressive strength determination, concrete samples were prepared by filling the moulds of dimensions 15 cm × 15 cm × 15 cm, ensuring the top surface was leveled off. A total of 18 cubes were cast, with fly ash replacing cement in six specimens. These specimens were initially covered with wet gunny bags for 24 hours before being removed and placed in a curing tank for the designated curing period. Upon completion of the curing period, the samples were taken out and immediately subjected to compressive strength testing using a Universal Testing Machine.

Table 4.5: Compressive Strength M30 on Cubes using Fly Ash

% Fly Ash	3 Days	7 Days	21 Days	28 Days	60 Days	90 Days
0%	10.13	13.86	26.12	31.27	44.52	45.59
5%	9.60	14.93	28.98	29.86	34.80	44.26
10%	9.06	9.32	24.17	24.35	37.60	48.53
15%	6.92	9.59	18.66	23.83	31.45	42.49
20%	5.33	10.13	17.07	22.92	36.26	47.86
25%	6.71	7.45	14.21	22.39	27.99	40.52

Fig.4.5: Compressive strength of M30 grade concrete at various % of Fly Ash

Observations from Graphs:

- Early Strength (3–7 Days):
 - Strength drops with increasing fly ash, especially beyond 10%.
 - Fly Ash slows early hydration, which delays strength gain.
- 28-Day Strength:
 - Peak 28-day strength is seen in the 0% mix (31.27 MPa).
 - Fly Ash content above 10% results in noticeable reduction in 28-day strength.
- Long-Term Strength (60–90 Days):
 - Significant strength recovery and even enhancement after 60–90 days for mixes with 10–20% Fly Ash.
 - 10% Fly Ash gives the highest 90-day strength (48.53 MPa), even higher than control concrete.
- Optimal Fly Ash Content:
 - 10–20% Fly Ash seems optimal for long-term strength without drastically sacrificing early-age performance.
 - 25% Fly Ash shows decline across all age groups—suggesting diminishing returns beyond 20%.

5. CONCLUSION

The research on sustainable materials in rigid pavement construction highlights the potential of bamboo fiber, coconut fiber, human hair fiber, fly ash, and ground granulated blast furnace slag as viable alternatives to conventional materials. These materials offer significant environmental benefits, including waste reduction, lower carbon footprints, and improved resource

efficiency. Additionally, they enhance mechanical properties such as tensile strength, durability, and crack resistance in concrete, leading to longer-lasting pavements. The study demonstrates that integrating sustainable materials can result in cost-effective, eco-friendly infrastructure solutions without compromising performance. With further research and large-scale implementation, these materials have the potential to revolutionize pavement construction, fostering a more sustainable and resilient built environment for future generations.

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Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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